

Colonialism and Its Impacts on Modern Global Relations

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16147223>

Abstract

The bequests of European colonialism have continued to shape interactions between the developed and developing states in modern global politics. These impacts are inherent in economic inequalities, cultural imperialism, peace and conflict, and global governance. There is unequal global economic order, economic liberalism which favours the developed states and renders the developing states perpetually poor, they remain producers of raw materials for the manufacturing Global North. This study examines the impacts of European colonialism on today's global relations, with a focus on the nature of economic, social, cultural, and political relations between the developed and developing states in the post-colonial era. Using a qualitative research approach, this study also examines various mechanisms deployed by the Global North in their continuing exploitation of the Global South in the post-liberation period. The study reveals how the legacies of European colonialism created hierarchy in global governance, with the Global North dominating the United Nations Security Council, the most powerful organ of the United Nations Organization (UNO) and its agencies among which is the International Monetary Fund (IMF), dictating global economy in favour of the Global North. This study also reveals the level of cultural imposition, a system in which African value systems, customs and traditions were eroded and seen as inferior to the European value and cultural systems. For better understanding of the impacts of colonialism on modern global relations, it is imperative to consider economic dependencies and structural inequalities, neo-colonialism and global governance, and artificial borders and ethnic conflicts. This study contributes to the understanding of the nature of economic, social, cultural and political interactions between the developed and developing states in modern global politics.

Keywords: Legacies, Colonialism, Imperialism, Capitalism, Liberalism

Introduction

European colonialism has great impact on today world politics. It shapes foreign policies of nations in the modern international system, and national governance. The impacts of European colonialism on modern global relations among states manifest in economic dominance, cultural imperialism, peace and conflict and hierarchical international system. These shape interactions between the developed and developing states in modern time. Also, anomalies created during the partitioning of Africa in the city of Berlin, Germany known as Berlin Conference (1884-1885), where African continent was partitioned without cultural and ethnic consideration and shared among various European colonialists. This manifested in border disputes, political instability, irredentism, cultural imposition, and conflicts. The major powers in the international system pursue their interests aggressively with flagrant abuse of international laws and disrespect for territorial integrity of the less powerful states. Conversely, while European colonialism had numerous negatives, some scholars have argued some positives such as infrastructural development, education and improvement in health sector, and modernization.

The UN was instituted to promote global cooperation, peace and security and to foster harmony among states through international laws, entrenchment of democratic principles, sustainable peace and enduring stability, economic cooperation and cultural exchange. In principles, these are demonstration of a fair, just and all inclusive international system, but in practice, there still some level of injustice and interference, which have exacerbated relations among states. The impacts of European colonialism have continued to influence interactions between the developed and developing states in global politics. Based on the interests of some of the global powers, they continue to violate international laws with impunity, dominates the decision making process, dictates the world economy, interfering in the internal politics of the post-colonial states and imposing their whims and caprices on the less developed countries. Post-colonial theory provides a framework on how colonial states configuration, imperialism through free trade, socio-cultural imposition have continue to shape interactions between the developed and developing states in modern international system. However, the study examines the impacts of European colonialism and how they shape interactions between the developed and developing states in modern global politics.

Colonialism and Its Impacts On Modern Global Relations

Colonialism has far-reaching impacts on the Global South. Its legacies have continued to shape relations between the developed and developing states in the international system. It has created a global hierarchy among states in the international system, with the imposition of western culture and ideas on the former colonized states. Examples are the universality of human rights, language, art and architecture, education, among others. Many of these aspects of western civilization and culture were institutionalized and characterized the modern international governance system. International institutions such as the United Nations Organization (UNO), the International Monetary Fund (IMF) and the International Court of Justice (ICJ) are often portrayed as global on paper but in reality, they are representation of interests of the powerful nations in the international arena. The modern international system often demonstrates double standards, where the powerful states choose when to obey or disobey international laws with impunity. These institutions operate within the frameworks, interests and core values of the global powers. Fanon (1961) argued that “the colonial powers constructed racial hierarchies that dehumanized the colonized states and justified their exclusion from the decision making process” and this trend continues till date (Fanon, 1961).

The United Nations as a product of European colonialism was instituted to regulate relations among states. The five permanent members of the Security Council; “the United States, the United Kingdom, France, Russia and China are former colonial powers” (Anghie, 2005). The Security Council, regarded as the most powerful organ of the UN plays a central role in global governance as regard to the maintenance of international peace and security while the Non-Permanent Members of the Security Council are selected by the United Nations General Assembly through a vote where candidates require two-thirds majority of the total votes. Unlike the Permanent members of the Security Council, the non-permanent members only have powers of deliberation and recommendations on issues relating to global peace and security. The decision making rest in the hands of the five Permanent Members of the UN Security Council. The hierarchy created hinged on the level of military and economic powers of member-states. This was evidence in the signing of 1968 Nuclear Non-Proliferation Treaty (NNPT), which was targeted at preventing the spread of nuclear weapons and promoting disarmament (Joyner, 2011). The treaty was negotiated and agreed upon in the peak of the cold war between the United States of America and the Union of Soviet Socialist Republic (USSR). The treaty prohibits non-nuclear states

from acquiring nuclear weapons. That is, “the ‘Haves’ should not help the ‘Have not’ to have while the ‘Have not’ should not seek to have” (Kissinger, 1969).

The Nuclear Non-Proliferation Treaty (NNPT) was instituted to prevent other nations from acquiring nuclear weapons so that the super powers or the ‘haves’ could achieve their foreign policy agendas through military and economic powers. The central aim of the Nuclear Non-Proliferation Treaty (NNPT) was to maintain a bi-polar international system. The Nuclear Non-Proliferation Treaty has been criticized for creating a system of nuclear apartheid, where the less-developed states are denied the avenue to develop nuclear technology to deter aggressors (Charles, 2014). However, states will continue to seek to develop nuclear technology when they are faced with significant military threats to their security. Examples of these countries that defied the treaty to develop nuclear technology are Israel, North Korea, and Iran nuclear project still ongoing despite various sanctions by the United States and its allies. Israel acquired nuclear weapon to uphold its existence in the Middle East and defend itself against external aggression. Scholars have argued that states have seen the development of nuclear technology as an important project for self-defense and deterrence. Therefore, acquiring nuclear weapons will serve as deterrence to any aggressor. The powerful states in the international system, who were signatories to the “Nuclear Non-Proliferation Treaty” (NNPT), have violated the terms and provisions of the treaty by aiding states of their strategic economic interests to acquire nuclear technology while placing economic sanctions on other states with the same motives.

Global Economic Order

Liberalism, an economic ideology deployed by the Global North in the exploitation of their former colonial states (the Global South). Liberalism emphasizes free trade, individual rights and democracy. These principles negate colonial practices of economic exploitation, cultural imposition, and infringement on people’s fundamental rights. The Global North dictated the world economy through several instruments. During colonial rule in Africa and other parts of the world, the European colonial powers depended on agricultural raw materials and mineral resources from their colonies. They exploited their colonies’ natural resources and promoted cash crops production of rubber, cotton, cocoa, rubber, cloves, palm oil and kernel among other agricultural and natural resources (Abernethy, 2000). The colonized states became a source of agricultural raw materials for European manufacturing

companies in Europe and Americas. More so, the legacies of European colonialism further promoted inequality and increased poverty in the former colonized states due to the level of exploitation of their resources. This has over the years made the former colonized nations to be solely dependent on the Global North for socio-economic survival, especially, their former colonial masters. Several Global South states have incurred foreign debts, some of which were inherited from their colonial past and borrowings after independence. Countries such as Benin Republic owed France, her formerly colonial master approximately \$1.2 billion, Cameroon \$2.3 billion. States formerly colonized by Britain are also indebted to it. Ghana owed the United Kingdom approximately \$1.4 billion, Kenya \$2.3 billion, Nigeria \$3.5 billion (IMF, 2019). These debts incurred by several developing states undermined their development and overly reliance on foreign aids.

Globalization is skewed in favour of the Global North. The Global South because of their level of development is the primary producers of raw materials while the Global North is the producers of goods. The exploitative tendencies of colonial legacies continue to shape global economy, with Multinational Corporations and International Financial Institutions exploiting the Global South under pretence of promoting economic growth and development. The legacies of European colonialism as regards to global governance reflect in the establishment of various international agencies of the United Nations Organization such as the International Monetary Fund (IMF), International Labour Organization (ILO), Food and Agricultural Organization (FAO) and the World Bank (WB). These agencies, particularly the IMF and the World Bank, create unequal relationships between the Global North and the Global South through mechanisms such as disparity of interest rate, conditional lending and other unfavourable terms and conditions in loans acquisition and repayment. These financial institutions imposed policies and programmes on the Global South. Example of such policies is the Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP), which was imposed on the borrowing states by instructing them to implement policies that directly benefited the Global North. Such policies and programmes include privatization and deregulation and trade liberalization (Stiglitz, 2002). More so, loan conditions often benefited the Global North while the Global South struggle to measure up with the loan repayment due to unfavourable terms and conditions. Sometimes, the IMF and the World Bank set debt trap for the Global South by granting more loans to them to service existing debts. This has led to financial

dependency, which makes it difficult for borrowing states to pursue independence economic policies (Woods, 2006).

More so, the International Monetary Fund's quota system grants more voting powers to the Global North, particularly the United States, Britain, France, Germany having the largest share of voting in decision making processes. The IMF and the World Bank have been promoting market fundamentalism, which creates unequal distribution of wealth and giving advantage to the developed countries (Woods, 2006). It is worthy of note that the Global South is having less representation in International Monetary Fund (IMF). The Global North dominates the decision making body of international financial institutions such as the IMF and the Paris Club. Over the years, these international financial institutions have been criticized for lacking transparency and accountability (Stiglitz, 2002).

Cultural Impact of Colonialism

Cultural imperialism, as a legacy of European colonialism has continue to shape cultural interactions between the Global North and the Global South in post-colonial international system in which African value system, customs and traditions have been eroded and seen as inferior to the Global North cultural and value systems. The manifestation of this was the adoption of foreign languages as the official languages of the former colonized states. In the British colonized states, English is the official language that is widely spoken in the public domains while French, Portuguese, Belgian, Italian and Spanish languages were adopted as official languages in states colonized by aforementioned colonial powers. The dominance of English and French languages is evidence in international forums. Western foods, clothes, and music are imported and make the colonized states to believe that they are superior to their local foods, fabrics and music. Cultural imperialism has promoted the cultures of the Global North at the expense of the Global South cultures.

More so, European colonialism created racial and ethnic divisions, resulting in violent conflicts. Racism has become a global concern. Africans and the entire black race across the world are subjected to all forms of racial discrimination in Europe and other parts of the world. There is also loss of traditional knowledge. The European colonialism disrupted traditional crafts and indigenous technology. African civilizations such as the Ife, Benin and the Nok cultures in Nigeria, the Ashanti civilization in Ghana, the Egyptian civilization among other civilizations that occurred in Africa from the 5th century B.C are

evidences of Africa's high level of ingenuity and development that were interrupted by Trans- Atlantic Slave Trade and colonialism which would have propelled Africa to the highest stage of socioeconomic growth and development. Walter Rodney argued that European powers exploitation of Africa's natural resources, labour, destruction of African textile industries, and disruption of Africa's cultures and creation of artificial borders were the factors responsible for Africa's underdevelopment (Rodney, 1972). He argued further that Africa's dependence on European investments limited their economic independence and resulting in perpetuation of poverty and limited economic growth (Rodney, 1972).

Cultural hierarchy created by the European colonialism has continued to shape modern world politics. Said, (1978) argues that colonial discourse produced the "Orient" as exotic and inferior to the West. This 'orientalist' tale continues in development policies by often casting non-Western societies as dependent on the West for guidance. More so, foreign aid initiatives are often portray the Global South as underdeveloped, lack capacity to govern self and constantly depending on their former colonial masters for technical knowhow. The aids given to the post-colonial states inform of cash or expertise is used to exploit the beneficiaries of such aids natural resources in what is referred to as neocolonialism. This is underscored by Escobar (1995), who demonstrates how the institutionalization of post-war development agendas shaped the colonized states through constant need of external interventions in infrastructural development, economic revival, conflict, diseases and control and technological transfer.

Psychological and Social Impact of Colonialism

The psychological and social impacts of colonialism are also paraphernalia of modern global politics. Fanon (1961) observes that colonial violence has both physical impacts on the colonized states and also stripped them of their cultural identities, a nostalgia that reflects on modern economic, social and political structures. It has created inferiority complex in the Global South, which forced them to conform to the whims and caprices of the Global North and their styles of governance and development, even when they negate their values, customs and traditions. Said (2004) argues that globalization reinforces these dynamics, homogenizing cultures while masking structural inequalities. Consequently, many post-colonial states navigate global politics from a position of dependency, unable to assert their socio-economic and political blueprint for development.

The feminist approach to the discourse is the politics and support for women rights in the developing countries. The non-Western women are portrayed as being oppressed and need liberation by the Western Powers through various institutions and the Global Civil Society Organizations advocating gender equality and Women's rights. Mohanty (1988), in her feminist critique under Western views, highlights how colonialism constructed non-Western women as oppressed. This trend has continued to shape foreign policies of the Global North and developmental programmes such as the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The U.S intervention in Afghanistan was seen as an effort towards the emancipation of the oppressed women, obscuring broader geopolitical motives while also reinforcing stereotypes about non-Western societies. However, these representations sustain the Western idea of superiority over the colonized states and perceived marginalization of the non-Western women in decision making process and socio-economic and political participation in their own states.

Colonialism, Artificial Borders and Ethnic Conflicts

The impact of European colonialism also manifests in conflicts arising from border disputes across the globe, which strains relations among states in the international system. The European colonial powers carved artificial borders that are causing conflicts among states across the world. "In Asia, there are border disputes between China-India over the Himalayan border region, India-Pakistan over Kashmir region, Laos-Thailand over the Mekong river region and Indonesia-Malaysia over Borneo border" (International Crisis Group, 2019). "In the Middle East, border disputes created by European colonialism are Iraq-Iran over the Shatt al-arab region, Kuwait-Iraq over Rumaila oil field region and Israel-Palestine over the West Bank and Gaza Strip" (Zahlan, 1984). "In Africa, there are border disputes between Ghana-Togo, Algeria-Morocco over Western Sahara, Eritrea-Ethiopia over Badme region, Kenya-Somalia over Gedo region, Chad-Libya over the oil rich Aouzou strip"(Cliffe, 1999).. "In addition, in Americas, border disputes created by European colonialism, among which are Haiti-Dominican Republic over the border on the Island of Hispaniola, Belize-Guatemala over Peten region and Guyana-Venezuela over Essequibo region" (Bulkan, 2017).

More so, across the world, there are issues of irredentism due to ethnic and cultural ties of groups. The anomalies created by the European colonial powers during the Berlin Conference 1884-1885 has led to violent conflicts in several countries such as Somali civil war which started in 1991, Eritrean-Ethiopian

war 1998-2000, Indo-Pakistani wars 1947, 1965, and 1971, and North Korea's aggression over South Korea among others. Most of these irredentist claims are still unresolved (Chazan, 1991).

More so, the European colonial powers implement policies, which impacted on the political development of the colonized countries even after independence. It impacted on local institutions, leading to bad governance and political instability. In Africa for instance, post-colonial states from 1960 witnessed several military coup de tats and civil wars due to the colonial powers' configuration of various states with authoritarianism. It was done without regards for ethnic and cultural identity of various groups in the continent of Africa and beyond. This arrangement undermined peaceful coexistence and development. In contemporary international system, there is vigorous campaign against dictatorial rule, which was used to rule over post colonized states.

Resources Exploration and Its Impact on the Global South

Environmental exploitation is also a legacy of European colonialism that remains evident in contemporary world economic order. Environmental exploitation ranges from resource extraction, deforestation leading to land degradation (Okech, 2018). The European colonial powers exploited the colonized states natural resources resulting in environmental degradation and depletion. This pattern continues till date, with the Global South bearing the brunt of climate change. In Ghana, gold mining led to deforestation, soil erosion and water pollution (Mwaura, 2019). In South Africa, Angola, and Democratic Republic of Congo, diamond mining in the aforementioned territories resulted in land degradation, water pollution and displacement. This trend continues till date, with several Global North companies carrying out mining activities in developing states across the world (Okech, 2018). The cascading effect of environmental degradation, logging, bush burning and other unethical environmental practices are the major causes of climate change, resulting in environmental challenges (UNFCCC, 2020). Climate change is a global concern, which requires collective action to avert global disaster. It is a global issue influencing relations among states in the international system and national politics. Programmes and resolutions adopted by the UN include Paris Agreement 2015. The agreement was aimed at limiting global temperature rise to below 2 degrees Celsius and effort towards limiting it to 1.5 degree Celsius (UN, 2015). Another initiative taken by the United Nations towards addressing climate change challenges is the institutionalization of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Goal

13 of the United Nations' SDGs focuses on taking urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts. There is also Climate Action Summit 2019, where the United Nations Secretary General, Antonio Guterrez called on leaders to work in synergy with the UN to present workable plans to enhance their nationally contributions to reduce greenhouse gas emissions for healthy living, peace and sustainable development (UNFCCC, 2019).

Furthermore, climate change policies often clash with economic interests of states in the international arena. For instance, the oil (fossil fuel) producing states under the leadership of Organization of Petroleum Exporting Countries (OPEC) have seen advocacy against fossil fuel by the developed states, especially the non-oil producing states as a threat to its members' economic survival and development. OPEC is a powerful influence in the international politics, rallying member-countries to vote in a bloc on global issues. This has led to tension in global politics. OPEC members have divergent views on climate change. On one hand, they acknowledged the need to address the issue of climate change and reaffirmed their commitment to the Paris 2016 Agreement, in which all thirteen (13) members were signatories to the agreement. However, OPEC members also committed to increasing oil production and rely on oil exports, which make it challenging to reduce greenhouse gas emissions. Major players in the global oil exploration have seen climate and its advocates as saboteurs working to undermine their economic activities. They argue that developed countries' advocacy towards reduction of greenhouse gas emissions would have significant impact on their economies (Bazilian, et al. 2018).

To mitigate the impact of climate change, OPEC members have rather supported financial compensation for any serious impacts of climate change mitigating measures. They demanded for a balance approach that supports effort towards reducing the impacts of climate change and at the same time promoting their economies. Some OPEC members have taken actions towards diversifying their economies. This can be seen in their investments in renewable energy sources. Leading Organization of Petroleum Exporting Countries such as Saudi Arabia and United Arab Emirate (UAE), Venezuela, Iraq, Kuwait have taken giant stride in renewable energy sources investing billions of dollars (UNFCCC, 2022). OPEC members are aware of the need to address climate challenges but in such a way that will not impact heavily on their economic interests while discharging their environmental responsibilities.

The persistence of colonial legacies in contemporary global politics highlights the need for structural reforms that will create a more equitable global socio-economic, cultural and political order. The post-colonial theory proponents advocate for the decolonization of international institutions, amplifying the voices of post-colonial states, prioritizing their interests. Initiatives such as South-South Cooperation and the Non-alignment Movement are potential pathways for the Global South to assert their control and challenge neo-colonial power dynamics (Young, 2001). It is also imperative for post-colonial states to promote epistemic diversity and reject the universality of Western ideas, a pathway to address structural inequalities rooted in European colonialism.

Positive Impacts of Colonialism Om Global South

It is worthy of note that while colonialism had numerous negative impacts which continue to shape interactions between Global North and Global South in modern global system, it also have some positive impacts. Infrastructural development, such as railways, bridges, roads and ports (sea and air) which facilitated trade, easier and faster means of transportation and communication are products of western civilization. Former colonized states have continue to partner with the developed nations in the areas of infrastructural development and technology transfer.

Colonialism also ushered-in western education and orthodox healthcare system, which have positively impacted on the well-being of the people in the developing states across the world. Western education improved literacy rates and ease communication between the developed and the developing countries. European missionaries played a significant role in the establishment of schools and hospitals. These legacies have continue to impact on the development of education and healthcare system in the developing states globally. Africa for instance had developed its informal educational system and traditional medicine prior to European colonialism but not as advanced as the western educational system and orthodox medicine.

Conclusion

The impacts of European colonialism on contemporary world politics are complex and multifaceted as seen above. They are embedded in contemporary global politics, shaping the foreign policies of states and global governance systems. These legacies reflect in the socio-economic, cultural and environmental inequalities that continue to marginalize the developing states. The legacies created

unequal economic relationships in which post-colonial states largely depend on their former colonial masters for survival. Many former colonies are hugely indebted to their former masters. They rely on them for aids, technical assistance, and loans. Colonialism established a hierarchy international system, with the developed states wielding significant powers and influence in the international system. Post-colonial theory provides a critical framework for understanding dynamics of relations between the developed and developing states. Culturally, European colonialism imposed western cultural norms and institutions on colonized states thereby relegating their indigenous cultural values. European colonialism also creates social injustice, a system that continues to shape relations between the developed and developing states till date.

The colonial powers enjoy all privileges in the modern international system while the post-colonial states are treated as subordinates and territories destined to be exploited. The legacies of European colonialism have contributed to various conflicts between states over artificial borders created during the scramble and partition of Africa and other regions. Former colonial powers continue to assert their authority and powers on their former colonies using various tools of exploitation (neocolonialism). In the 20th century, there was a change in states' relations occasioned by nationalist movements especially in Europe and Africa, where nationalists emphasized the relevance of sovereignty and self-determination. This brought serious resistance to external influence. Several countries attained political independence but that cannot be said of the economic sovereignty. This has continued to shape states' relation in the modern international system. Addressing these structural inequalities will require having a global body that values diversity, equality, and genuine partnership between the developed and developing states or among states in the international community that will be of mutual benefits. Nonetheless, there are few positive impacts of European colonialism on the former colonized states as elucidated above.

Way Forward

Addressing the negative impacts of colonialism on relations between the developed and the developing states in contemporary global politics requires a multifaceted approach. There is need for restitution for injustices in the pre and post-colonial era. This can help address ongoing disparities. Acknowledgement

of socio-economic and political injustices can help facilitate healing and reconciliation for the promotion of global peace and enduring stability.

Global cooperation and dialogue can help foster equitable relations between the Global north and Global south through international organizations such as the United Nations and its agencies, which serves as forums for interactions among states in the international system. The developed nations should support the preservation and promotion of indigenous cultures, languages and traditions which can help revitalize cultural identity. There is need to develop an inclusive and equitable economic order that reflect fairness and inclusiveness. The developing states need to develop initiatives, such as entrepreneurship, infrastructural development and sustainable resource management. This can help reduce dependencies and promote self-sufficiency.

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